

Chromatographic Separations of Certain Metallic Ions Using Solutions of Certain Schiff-Bases in the Mobile Phase

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Chromatographic separations of certain closely resembling metallic ions, which are involved in various important special alloys have been effected over plain and impregnated papers, thin layers of silica gel and cellulose. Solutions of certain Schiff-bases derived from Vanillin in pure and mixed solvents were used for irrigating plain papers and thin layers spotted with the metallic ions, while a series of polar and nonpolar solvents constitute the mobile phase in case of the impregnated papers. The results obtained with these techniques have been compared with those obtained using paper electrophoresis and have been discussed in the light of the phenomenon of the coordination.

THE involvement of the phenomenon of coordination (or complex formation) in chromatographic separations of metallic ions has been established well, not only for the detection of the ion on paper but also for the development of the chromatogram. In recent years an increasing emphasis has been laid on the use of complexing agents in the mobile phase for effecting differential migration of the ions on paper, as complex formation has been suggested as one of the important phenomena responsible for the adsorption and desorption of the metallic ions on paper¹. This has also encouraged the use of impregnated papers. In the present work an attempt has been made to study the separations of some of the closely resembling metallic ions, important not only from the point of view of qualitative separations, but also with reference to the compositions of various important special alloys used in the high tensile-steels for supersonic jets, rockets and missiles which present difficult separations.^{2,3} The mobile phase used for these separations consists in solutions of Schiff-bases derived from vanillin and sulphanilic acid (VS), anthranilic acid (VA) and hydrazine (VH) in pure and mixed solvents. While the stationary phase involved plain and impregnated (with a 2% ethanol solution of VS, VA or VH) papers and thin layers of cellulose and silica gel. The results obtained with these techniques have been compared with those obtained with paper electrophoresis and discussed on the basis of phenomenon of coordination.

Experimental

Whatman No 1 filter paper discs of diameter 11 cm were used for paper chromatographic separations using Rutter's technique of radial development⁴, with the wicks (width 2 mm and length 2-3 cm) having tapering free ends.

For the preparation of *impregnated papers*, these discs were soaked in an alcoholic solutions (2% w/v) of VA or VH [some of the discs were soaked in an aqueous solution of VH (2% w/v)] and then dried in an inert atmosphere at room temperature and stored in polythene bags.

For TLC, Atlantis, TLC apparatus model ATLC-2, was used. Thin layers of cellulose (Chromatographic, BDH) and silica gel (German, Chromatographic) (Thickness 0.5 mm) were prepared on glass plates of $8\frac{1}{2} \times 8\frac{1}{2}$ " with the applicator supplied with the kit. The plates were dried at room temperature and then activated at 110° for 2 hrs. The chromatograms were developed in the air-tight glass chamber supplied with the kit.

AR grade soluble salts of Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Cr(VI), Mn(II), Pb(II), Al(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Bi(III), Sn(II), Be(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Ag(I), Ce(IV), Mo(VI), W(VI), V(IV), Tl(IV) and Pt(IV) were dissolved in doubly distilled water to get stock solutions (0.1M) of the metallic ions.

For the irrigation of the plain papers or the thin layers, 0.01M alcoholic solutions of VA, VH and VS were used. The effect of the presence of acid in the solvent on the mobilities of the ions was studied by mixing 1M HCl or acetic acid with the alcoholic solutions of VA or VH in the ratio (volume to volume basis), VA/VH : acid, 5 : 1, 10 : 1, 20 : 1, and 25 : 1. The solvents used with the impregnated papers involve chromatographic pure organic solvents, ethanol, dimethyl ketone, dioxane, ethyl acetate and chloroform. The effect of the presence of acid in the mobile phase was studied by mixing ethanol with 1M HCl or acetic acid in the ratio (v/v) 10 : 1 (the ratio which gave better separations with TLC

studies). The effect of the impregnation on the mobilities of the metallic ions was also studied and compared with the use of the standard solvent mixture⁵, acetic acid, ethyl acetate and HCl(2*M*) in the ratio (v/v) 9 : 9 : 2 for the separation of Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions.

For paper-electrophoretic studies, horizontal paper electrophoresis tank and the accompanying power supply were used, with the Whatman No 1 filter paper strips of 300 × 40 mm size.

The electrolyte solutions used for the study were 0.01*M* alcoholic solutions of VA and VH, 0.01*M* aqueous solution of sodium salt of VS, VA-pyridine buffer of pH 6.03; VS-pyridine buffer of pH 5.90 and VH-acetic acid (2*M*) mixture (10 : 1) of pH 3.95.

TABLE 1—Rf-VALUES OF CERTAIN METALLIC IONS ON PAPER DISCS

Paper = Whatman No. 1			Time—2 hrs				
Metallic Ions	Rf-values × 100			Metallic Ions	Rf-values × 100		
	Solvents				Solvents		
	A	B	C		A	B	C
Be(II)	77	78	87	Al(III)	78	76	100
Mg(II)	74	68	100	Fe(III)	81	81	100
Ca(II)	72	66	91	Cr(III)	83	83	100
Sr(II)	83	97	87	Ce(IV)	51	81	95
Ba(II)	50	97	79	Pt(IV)	97	60	92
Fe(II)	25	21	100	As(III)	38	35	90
Co(II)	26	17	90	V(IV)	61	56	100
Ni(II)	73	71	100	U(VI)	81	82	100
Cu(II)	45	30	100	Zr(IV)	83	81	100
Mn(II)	23	31	100	Mo(VI)	31	56	93
Pb(II)	53	50	88	W(VI)	65	67	100
Zn(II)	17	72	100	Cr(VI)	65	65	97
Hg(II)	85	87	82				
Bi(II)	84	88	100				
Cd(II)	71	70	98				
Sn(II)	94	90	92				

Spotting of the metallic ions was done by micropipette of 1 ml (~0.02 ml per drop). After the spots had been dried, development was carried out by irrigating with the required solvent for the required time, in air-tight chambers, previously saturated with the vapours of the solvent concerned.

The paper discs, strips or the Tl-plates (after marking the solvent front in case of paper chromatography and TLC) were dried at room temperature and the positions of the metallic ions were detected using suitable spray reagents⁵. For the calculations of Rf-values (ratio of movement of the ion and the solvent) the distance from the centre of the spot to the starting point was taken, while for electrophoretic studies the distance moved by the ion from the point of the application has been taken. The results obtained are given in Tables 1-4; while the separational possibilities in binary, ternary and polynary mixtures are recorded in Tables I-III.

TABLE 3—Rf-VALUES OF METALLIC IONS ON FILTER PAPER STRIPS BY DESCENDING METHOD

Paper = Whatman No. 1		Time—2 hrs		
Metallic Ions	Rf-values × 100			
	A	B	C	
Mg(II)	78 ^{..}	79	89	
Al(III)	82 ^{..}	86	80 ^{..}	
Mn(II)	53 ^{..}	88.	90	
Zn(II)	80 ^{..}	69	62 ^{..}	
Fe(II)	59 ^{..}	78 ^{..}	90	
Fe(III)	55 ^{..}	49.3 ^{..}	81	
Cr(III)	0	0	0	
Zr(IV)	0	0	0	
V(IV)	89 ^{..+}	75 ^{..}	87 ^{..}	
Mo(VI)	29 ⁺	47 ^{..}	48 ^{..}	
W(VI)	72	55 ^{..}	53 ^{..}	
Ti(IV)	96	86	93	
U(VI)	41 ^{..}	56.8 ^{..}	86 ^{..}	
Co(II)	84 ^{..}	58.4 ^{..}	90	
Ni(II)	55 ^{..}	81.9 ^{..}	89	
Cu(II)	80.9 ^{..}	64.1 ^{..}	92	

^{..} Diffused.
^{..} Broad Band.
⁺ Tailings.

TABLE 2—Rf-VALUES OF CERTAIN METALLIC IONS ON THE LAYERS OF SILICA GEL AND CELLULOSE

Metallic Ions	Activation time—2 hrs. at 110°C ;								Run time—1 hr. at 30°C									
	Silica gel ; Rf-values × 100								Cellulose ; Rf-values × 100									
	Solvents								Solvents									
	B	A	D	E	F	H	J	L	A	C	D	E	G	H	I	J	K	M
Cu(II)	11.0 ^{..}	11.8 ^{..}	59	60 ^{..}	45.3	10.8	79 ^{..}	64	2.6 ^{..}	100 ^{..}	21.8 ^{..}	28.9 ^{..}	64 ^{..}	7.4 ^{..}	28.1 ^{..}	28 ^{..}	60.4	17.8 ^{..}
Ni(II)	35 ⁺	16.5 ^{..}	71 ⁺	48 ⁺	41.4 ⁺	76	67	75	30.6 ^{..}	87 ^{..}	62.7 ⁺	43.5	70 ⁺	38.5 ^{..}	42.2 ^{..}	41.8 ^{..}	57 ^{..}	38.8 ^{..}
Co(II)	7.6 ^{..}	5.5 ^{..}	63	50	42.1 ⁺	76.8 ⁺	67	71	3.3 ^{..}	83 ^{..}	24.2 ^{..}	23.1 ^{..}	60 ^{..}	7.4 ^{..}	20.8 ^{..}	27.1 ^{..}	52 ^{..}	15 ^{..}
Fe(II)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	86 ⁺	43.7 ⁺	63	67.7	0	32.8 ^{..}	37.7 ^{..}	61 ^{..}	22.6 ^{..}
Mo(VI)	9.1	6.2 ^{..}	57 ⁺	50 ⁺	40.6 ^{..}	7.9 ^{..}	57 ⁺	25 ^{..}	—	100	51 ^{..}	22.4	63.2 ^{..}	0	9.3 ^{..}	17.5 ^{..}	21.9 ^{..}	90.2 ^{..}
V(IV)	14	10.2 ^{..}	50	45 ^{..}	42.9 ^{..}	32.6 ^{..}	61	25 ^{..}	13.3 ^{..}	88 ^{..}	56.9 ^{..}	50.7	67.7 ^{..}	39.5 ^{..}	42.5 ^{..}	50.8 ^{..}	66 ^{..}	38.3 ^{..}
Zr(IV)	20 ^{..}	0	0	0	0	0	62 ^{..}	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ti(IV)	16	7	0	55	51.5	7.2	66	35	16.6	94	0	71 ^{..}	85.1	37.7	86.5	71	85	81.5
Fe(III)	9.1 ^{..}	8.6 ^{..}	61	31 ^{..}	25.7 ^{..}	33.3 ⁺	60	15	30	47 ^{..}	58.4 ^{..}	24.6	74.8 ^{..}	56.3 ^{..}	81.8 ⁺	50 ^{..}	73 ^{..}	74.6 ⁺
Al(III)	16	5.5 ^{..}	54	46 ⁺	31.2 ⁺	3.6 ^{..}	55 ^{..}	7 ^{..}	24 ^{..}	88 ^{..}	56.9	50.7	67.7 ^{..}	38.5 ^{..}	42.5 ^{..}	50.8 ^{..}	66 ^{..}	38.3 ^{..}
Mg(II)	11 ^{..}	28.3 ⁺	76	66	35.1	4.3	61 ^{..}	23	3.3	0	5.1	0	32.2	0	16.7 ^{..}	62	—	95.6

^{..} Diffusion,
⁺ Tailings.

TABLE 4—PAPER ELECTROPHORETIC MOBILITIES OF CERTAIN METALLIC IONS

Paper—Whatman No. 1.
c=cathodic ; a=anodic.
" = Broad Band.

Time—2 hrs.
Voltage—200 v.

Metallic Ions	Distance moved in mm by the ion					
	A	B	C	L	N	O
Fe(II)	5 c"	0	7 c"	0	22 c	5 c
Co(II)	7 c"	10 c	32 c"	15 c"	27 c"	34 c"
Ni(II)	7 c"	15 c	40 c"	18 c"	8 c"	31 c"
Cu(II)	9 c"	9.5 c"	44 c"	17 c	10 c"	30 c
Mn(II)	8 c"	0	5 c"	0	14 c	11 c
Zn(II)	13 c"	—	49 c"	27 c"	58 c"	42 c"
Al(III)	11 c"	10 c"	24 c"	22 c	18 c"	26 c"
Mg(II)	12.5 c	6 a"	7 a	20 a	14 c"	5 c
Zr(II)	0	0	7 c	0	0	6 c
V(IV)	10 c"	10 c"	23 c"	32 c"	26 c"	23 c"
U(VI)	0	7 c"	10 c"	0	15 c"	40 c"
W(VI)	8 a	7 a	12 c	7.5 c	8 c	9 c
Mo(VI)	7 a	4 a"	21 a"	5 a	8 c	20 a
Ti(IV)	6 c	7 c	5 c	14 c	8 c	4 c
Cr(III)	0	5 c	13 c	7 c	28 c"	10 c

The abbreviations used for the solvents in the Tables are as follows :

- A = Ethanolic Soln. of Van-An.
 B = Ethanolic Soln. of Van-Hy.
 C = Aq. Soln. of Na.-Sul-Van.
 D = A + HCl (1M) [10 : 1]
 E = A + HCl (1M) [20 : 1]
 F = A + HCl (1M) [25 : 1]
 G = A + HCl (1M) [5 : 1]
 H = A + Acetic acid (1M) [10 : 1]
 I = A + Acetic acid (1M) [5 : 1]
 J = B + HCl (1M) [10 : 1]
 K = B + HCl (1M) [5 : 1]
 L = B + Acetic acid (1M) [10 : 1]
 M = B + Acetic acid (1M) [5 : 1]
 N = A + Py. Buffer [pH 6]
 O = C + Py. Buffer [pH 5.9]

TABLE I—SEPARATION POSSIBILITIES OF METALLIC IONS USING CERTAIN SCHIFF BASES BINARY SYSTEMS

PC=Paper Chromatography (Radial) ;
 PE=Paper Electrophoresis ;
 TLS=Thin Layer (Silica) ;
 TLC=Thin Layer (Cellulose).

Ions Separated	Methods and Solvents	Ions Separated	Methods and Solvents
1. Fe(II), Co(II)	PC(C) ; PE (A,B,N,P)	21. Fe(III), V(IV)	PE(A,B,O)
2. Fe(II), Fe(III)	PC(A,B) ; TLC (C,H,J) ; PE (N,O,P)	22. Fe(III), Zr(IV)	PE(A,O) ; TLS(A)
3. Co(II), Ni(II)	PC(A,B,C) ; TLC(D)	23. Fe(II), Ni(II)	TLS(E) ; PE (A,B)
4. Co(II), Cu(II)	PC(C) ; TLS (D,E,H)	24. Fe(II), Zn(II)	PE (A,B)
5. Co(II), Zn(II)	PC(C)	25. Fe(II), Cr(III)	PE (A,B,P)
6. Co(II), Mn(II)	PC(O), PE(B,C,P)	26. Mn(II), Zn(II)	PC(A,B) ; PE(C)
7. Cu(II), Ag(I)	PC(O)	27. Mn(II), Ni(II)	PE(B,C,P)
8. Cu(II), Mn(II)	PE(B,C,P)	28. Mn(II), Cr(III)	PE(B,P)
9. Cu(II), Fe(II)	PE(A,B,P)	29. Mo(VI), W(VI)	PE(C,I)
10. Cu(II), Zn(II)	PE(B)	30. Mo(VI), U(VI)	PE(C)
11. Cu(II), Ni(II)	TLC (A,D,J,M) , TLS (D,E,H)	31. Mo(VI), V(IV)	PE(C)
12. Cu(II), Fe(III)	TLS (E)	32. Mo(VI), Zr(IV)	PE(C)
13. Cu(II), Cr(III)	PE(A)	33. Mo(VI), Cr(III)	PE(C)
14. Fe(III), Ni(II)	TLS(D)	34. Zr(IV), V(IV)	PE(A)
15. Fe(III), Co(II)	TLS(D,E)	35. U(VI), V(IV)	PE(A,P)
16. Fe(III), Mn(II)	PE(O,P)	36. Al(III), Cr(III)	PC(A)
17. Fe(III), Cr(III)	PE(O)	37. Be(II), Mg(II)	PC(B,C)
18. Fe(III), Mo(VI)	TLS(A), PE(B,C,O)	38. Be(II), Al(III)	PC(C)
19. Fe(III), W(VI)	PE(B,C,O)	39. Mg(II), Al(III)	PC(B) ; TLS(A,B) ; TLC(D,J) ; PE(B,C,O,P)
20. Fe(III), U(VI)	PF(A,B,O,P)	40. Sr(II), Ba(II)	PC(C)

TABLE II—SEPARATION POSSIBILITIES OF METALLIC IONS USING CERTAIN SCHIFF BASES
TERNARY SYSTEMS

PC=Paper Chromatography (Radial) ; PE=Paper Electrophoresis ;		TLS=Thin Layer (Silica) ; TLC=Thin Layer (Cellulose).	
Ions Separated	Methods and Solvents	Ions Separated	Methods and Solvents
41. Fe(II), Co(II), Cu(II)	TLS(H)	61. Fe(III), Ti(III), Cr(III)	PE(O)
42. Fe(II), Zn(II), Ni(II)	PE(B)	62. Fe(III), Mo(VI), Zr(IV)	TLS(H)
43. Fe(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)	PE(B)	63. Fe(III), V(IV), Zr(IV)	TLS(B) ; PE(N)
44. Fe(II), Co(II), Zn(II)	PE(B)	64. Fe(III), Ti(IV), Zr(IV)	TLS(B)
45. Fe(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)	TLS(H)	65. Fe(III), Cr(III), Mo(VI)	PC(A,B) ; PE(B,C)
46. Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II)	TLC(A,H,J)	66. Fe(III), W(VI), Cr(III)	PE(B)
47. Fe(II), Cr(III), Ni(II)	PE(B)	67. Fe(III), Mo(VI), U(VI)	PE(B)
48. Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)	TLS(B,H,L)	68. Fe(III), W(VI), U(VI)	PE(B)
49. Cu(II), Zn(II), Mn(II)	PE(B)	69. Fe(III), Mo(VI), W(VI)	PE(C)
50. Mn(II), Zn(II), Co(II)	PE(B)	70. Mo(VI), V(IV), Zr(IV)	TLC(A,B,H)
51. Zn(II), Mn(II), Ni(II)	PE(B)	71. Mo(VI), W(VI), U(IV)	PC(A,B) ; PE(A,P)
52. Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II)	PC(A,C)	72. Mo(VI), W(VI), Zr(IV)	PE(A,P)
53. Ag(I), Zn(II), Pb(II)	PC(A,B)	73. Mo(VI), W(VI), Ce(IV)	PC(A,B)
54. Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II)	PC(A)	74. Mo(VI), U(VI), Zr(IV)	PE(B)
55. Fe(III), Al(III), Mg(II)	TLS(A,B,E,L) ; TLC(A) ; PE(B)	75. Mo(VI), W(VI), Cr(III)	PE(A)
56. Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II)	TLC(H)	76. U(VI), V(IV), W(VI)	PE(A)
57. Fe(III), Al(III), Cr(III)	TLC(M,C)	77. Mo(VI), Ti(IV), Zr(IV)	TLS(B)
58. Fe(III), Fe(II), Mn(II)	PE(O)	78. Ti(IV), Zr(IV), V(IV)	TLS(A,H,L)
59. Fe(III), Mo(IV), Tl(VI)	PE(B,O)	79. W(VI), U(VI), Zr(IV)	PE(B)
60. Fe(III), Ti(IV), W(VI)	PE(B,O)		

TABLE III—SEPARATION POSSIBILITIES OF METALLIC IONS USING CERTAIN SCHIFF BASES
POLYNARY SYSTEMS

PC=Paper Chromatography (Radial) ; PE=Paper Electrophoresis ; TLS=Thin Layer (Silica) ; TLC=Thin Layer (Cellulose).	
Ion Separated	Method and Solvents
1. Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II)	PC(B)
2. Fe(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)	PC(A)
3. Cu(II), Zn(II), Pb(II), Ni(II)	PC(A,B)
4. Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)	PC(A)
5. Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)	TLS(A,L)
6. Fe(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II)	PC(B)
7. Fe(III), Mo(VI), Co(II), Ni(II)	TLC(M)
8. Fe(III), Mo(VI), Ti(IV), V(IV)	TLC(H)
9. Fe(III), Zn(VI), V(IV), Ti(IV)	TLC(H)
10. Zr(IV), Cr(III), Mo(VI), Fe(III)	PE(N)
11. Fe(III), Cr(III), Zr(IV), W(VI)	PE(N)
12. Fe(III), Cr(III), Zr(IV), Ti(VI)	PE(N)
13. Mo(VI), V(IV), Zr(IV), Ti(IV)	TLS(D) ; TLC(J)
14. Mo(VI), U(VI), Ce(IV), V(IV)	PC(A)
15. Fe(III), Mo(VI), V(IV), Zr(IV)	TLC(D)
16. Fe(III), Tl(VI), Mo(VI), Zr(IV)	TLC(J)
17. Mo(VI), Ce(IV), Zr(IV), V(IV)	PC(A)
18. Ag(II), Bi(III), Pb(II), Zn(II), Mn(II)	PC(C)
19. Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Ag(I), Pt(IV)	PC(A,B)
20. Fe(III), Mo(VI), V(IV), Cr(III), Ti(IV)	TLC(C)
21. Fe(III), Mo(VI), V(IV), Zr(IV), Tl(VI)	TLS(E), TLC(A,C,M)
22. V(IV), Ti(IV), Cu(II), Ni(II), Al(III)	TLS(L) ; TLC(D)
23. Mo(VI), Al(III), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II)	TLS(L), TLC(D)
24. Cu(II), Ag(I), Zn(II), Pb(II), Mn(II), Sn(IV)	PC(A,E)
25. Cu(II), Ag(I), Pt(II), Sn(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Bi(III), Cd(II)	PC(A)
26. Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Pb(II), Sn(II), Mn(II), Cd(II)	PC(A)

Results and Discussion

The important results obtained in this study

may be summarised as follows :

1. The mobilities of metallic ions on paper were found to increase with the Schiff base present in the solutions (used as the mobile phase) in the order : Van-Hy < Van-An < Van-Sul. TLC-Studies also indicated similar results (i.e. Van-An > Van-Hy).

2. Mobilities of ions on impregnated papers were found faster than on plain papers, while ethyl acetate, acetone, dioxane and chloroform failed to impart mobility to the metallic ions on impregnated papers, ethanol proved quite successful in doing so. However, a comparison of the mobilities of Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) with a standard solvent system, ethyl acetate, acetone and HCl (2M) in a (v/v) ratio 9 : 9 : 2, on plain and impregnated papers indicated slower mobilities on impregnated paper.

3. The presence of acid in the solvent was found to accelerate the mobilities of the ions. The acceleration was found greater with a strong acid (HCl) than with a weak acid (acetic acid). Although, effective separations could be affected in the absence of the acid. The spots were diffused in a number of cases. The presence of acid prevents the diffusion, but at the same time the effective separation is lost with HCl, whereas acetic acid helps it, particularly in case of Van-Hy.

4. Paper electrophoretic studies, using same solvents as with paper (or thin layers) did not give fruitful results, because of the overlapping of the bands. However, some better separations could be effected using pyridine buffers with Van-An and Van-Sul and Van-Hy-acetic acid mixture. Similarly, the descending chromatography with the filter paper

strips, using alcoholic solutions of these Schiff bases were found unsuccessful in effecting differential migration as practically every metal-ion was found to move with the solvent-front.

In the light of the above results, the following mechanism for paper chromatography may be suggested, with the use of solutions of complexing agents in the mobile phase, modifying slightly the working hypothesis of Janardhan and Paul¹. On plain papers the aquo cation may be considered adsorbed forming ion associated complex with cellulose, as suggested by Janardhan *et al*¹. On irrigating the paper with a solution of complexing agent (Ligand), the metal ion forms complex with the ligand replacing the bound water molecules partially or wholly. Thus, the metal ion, in the form of metal-ligand complex is only loosely held with the paper and comes in rather desorbed state. The solvent then washes this metal-complex on

The reverse order of mobility of the Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) on plain and impregnated paper, with the standard solvent system can also be understood in the light of lesser solubilities of these complexes in aquo-HCl resulting in the lesser mobilities on impregnated paper. The other components of the solvent—system, ethyl acetate and acetone have no solvating effect on these complexes. As the release or the presence of protons (acid) helps in desorption of the metal-ion, the observed order of mobilities of the metallic ions with the Schiff-base present in the solution : Van-Hy < Van-An < Van-Sul and the accelerating effects of the presence of acids, strong and weak (HCl and Acetic acid) can be explained in the light of their proton releasing tendencies (acid-strengths). The acid-strengths of Van-Hy, Van-An and Van-Sul, show an increasing trend with the replacement of hydrazine by anthranilic acid in Van-An(II) and by sulphanilic acid in Van-Sul(III)

(I) Van-Hy.

(II) Van-An.

(III) Van-Sul.

account of its solvating effect. The release (or presence) of protons during complex formation, however, helps in desorption due to displacement of the metal-ions.

Similarly, on impregnated papers, the presence of complexing agent (Ligand) in the stationary phase—results in the formation of metal-ligand complex during spotting of the aquo cation on paper in place of ion associated metal cellulose complex. Thus, the metal-ion remains rather desorbed in the form of metal-ligand complex and is washed away with the irrigating solvent due to its solvating effect for this complex. The release or presence of protons, plays its catalysing part in the desorption of the metal-ion here also.

Thus, in both the cases of plain and impregnated papers the differential migration of the metallic ions are due to difference in the solubilities of the metal-ligand complex in the solvent. The lack of mobilities of metallic ions on impregnated papers with pure organic solvents dioxane, ethylacetate, acetone and chloroform was associated with the insolubility of the metal-ligand complexes in these solvents. As these complexes are soluble in ethanol, it was found successful in giving mobilities to the metallic ions.

The greater mobilities of metallic ions in presence of HCl than acetic acid can similarly be understood. Lesser diffusion in presence of an acid is also associated with the ease of desorption of metal ions, thus giving more compact bands. HCl, being a strong acid, causes a levelling effect to the mobilities of metallic ions. Thus, acetic acid (a weak acid) was found more useful in giving effective separations.

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